

IMPROVEMENT OF ADMINISTRATIVE AND LEGAL MECHANISMS FOR ENSURING TRAFFIC SAFETY IN THE BODIES OF THE MINISTRY OF DEFENSE

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Abstract: The article provides a scientific analysis of the issues of improving the administrative and legal mechanisms for ensuring road safety in the bodies of the Ministry of Defense. The principles of "Safe and smooth road," operating in the international legal arena, are also explained in this direction.

The opinions of legal scholars on improving the administrative and legal mechanisms for ensuring road safety were analyzed. The legislation of foreign countries, such as the Russian Federation and a number of CIS countries, has been studied. Proposals and recommendations have been developed to improve the administrative and legal mechanisms for ensuring road safety in the bodies of the Ministry of Defense.

Key words: Road traffic, traffic accidents, legal norms, safe and smooth road, and the systematization of legislation.

INTRODUCTION

As is known, ensuring road safety, especially preventing road traffic accidents and minimizing their consequences, has become one of the urgent tasks today.

METHODS

Over the past period, our republic has implemented a number of organizational and legal measures in the field of road safety. In particular, the concept of road safety in Uzbekistan and the national program "Safe and Smooth Road" for 2022-2026 have been adopted and are being implemented. The main goal of reforms implemented in the field of road safety is, first and foremost, to strengthen legal guarantees for the protection of life and health of road users. In this regard, developing new and modern mechanisms for ensuring road safety, studying existing problems through scientific research in these areas, as well as developing and implementing the most effective methods for addressing them, is of great importance.

RESULTS

Despite this, road traffic accidents and the consequences of damage caused by them are increasing in our country. Specifically, 22.9% of traffic accidents were caused by non-compliance with the established speed limit. 7.1% were due to driver inexperience, 5.1% to not maintaining proper distance, 3.7% to not yielding to pedestrians, 2.9% to disobeying traffic lights or road signs, 2.8% to violating overtaking rules, 1% to driving under the influence of alcohol, and 8.7% to other reasons. 45.5% of accidents were caused by objective reasons. These include the lack of pedestrian crossings - 11%, absence of bicycle lanes - 8.3%, lack of road dividers - 8.1%, insufficient road lighting - 5.2%, and wet or icy road conditions - 1.9%. The service also included in this category the absence of barriers (fences) to restrict pedestrian movement - 4.6%, narrow roads not adapted to traffic flow - 4.3%, and lack of

underground and overground pedestrian crossings - 1.7%. Almost half of all accidents - 46.8% - involve vehicles hitting pedestrians. Car collisions accounted for 31.8%, collisions with cyclists for 8.4%, vehicle rollovers for 5.3%, collisions with obstacles for 4.4%, and collisions with parked vehicles for 1.2%.

Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to strengthen the administrative and legal means of ensuring road safety, particularly by establishing liability for acts that currently fall outside the scope of responsibility, and to improve the procedure for handling cases of this category of administrative offenses.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.

If we examine the opinions of legal scholars on this matter, including A.A. Tashtemirov and S.A. Kalauov, they argue that the existence of nearly 500 regulatory legal acts in the field of road safety today negatively affects their correct and effective application in systematizing and improving legislation in the field of road safety.[2]

According to A.K. Yangibayev and M. Alimov, problems in the field of road safety can be observed as a result of drivers' disregard for traffic rules established by regulatory legal acts, their inexperience, non-compliance of roads with established requirements, and pedestrians' failure to follow rules as participants in traffic, leading to accidents and violations.[3]

In our view, the existence of approximately 500 regulatory legal acts in the field of road safety indicates the need for their unification in improving administrative and legal mechanisms for ensuring road safety. Meanwhile, drivers' disregard for traffic rules established by regulatory legal acts, their inexperience, non-compliance of roads with established requirements, and pedestrians' failure to follow rules as participants in road traffic signify a lack of adherence to driving culture and insufficient knowledge in this area. Therefore, we believe it is necessary to teach the subject of "driving culture" in all driving schools in our country.

Additionally, the number of traffic accidents caused by drunk driving is increasing year by year. For instance, violations of Article 131 of the Code of Administrative Offenses (evasion of examination to determine intoxication of vehicle drivers and other traffic participants) were recorded as follows: 26,814 in 2019, 23,063 in 2020, 25,680 in 2021, 23,960 in 2022, and 23,178 in 2023.[4] This not only leads to more severe punishments but also creates conditions for serious traffic accidents. This, along with aggravating the type of punishment, creates the basis for the occurrence of serious traffic accidents.

In our current legislation on administrative responsibility, there are still acts that fall outside the scope of administrative liability. For example, the unclear disposition of Article 136 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan causes various problems and objections from officials in applying this article. Specifically, according to the norm's disposition, drivers' refusal to undergo examination to determine intoxication from alcohol, drugs, or other substances in the prescribed manner entails appropriate liability. However, the commission of this offense under the influence of analogues of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances logically falls outside the scope of responsibility and creates a controversial situation in applying the law.

Therefore, in our opinion, it is advisable to provide for liability in Article 136 of the Code of Administrative Offenses for evading examination to determine whether drivers of vehicles and other traffic participants are under the influence of alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs,

their analogues, psychotropic substances, or other substances that affect an individual's intellect.

Currently, there are several problems in the timely and quality detection of road traffic accidents, prosecution of perpetrators, and minimization of accident consequences, without which traffic safety cannot be ensured. In particular, there are many cases where accident participants leave the scene in violation of established rules or attempt to repair vehicles involved in accidents to conceal evidence of violations. As a result, the ability of internal affairs bodies or the Military Traffic Control Inspectorate of the Ministry of Defense to conduct high-quality and impartial investigations is diminishing, and evidence of traffic accidents is being lost.

Notably, the lack of accountability for unauthorized repair of vehicles involved in traffic accidents, which leads to the loss of significant evidence during pre-investigation checks, remains one of the main reasons for the aforementioned problematic issues.

Therefore, in our opinion, it is advisable to supplement the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a separate norm of the following content:

"Article 137-1. Arbitrary repair of vehicles damaged by a traffic accident.

Arbitrary repair of vehicles that have caused a traffic accident without the permission of the responsible employees of the internal affairs bodies, if this action leads to the loss of evidence during the pre-investigation check, - entails the imposition of a fine from five to ten times the base calculation amount."

In practice, problems related to the expiration of the term of administrative responsibility before the detection of the offender as a result of the unknown person committing a traffic accident and hiding from the scene of the accident are of particular importance. In particular, as a result of such cases, the problems of ensuring the inevitability of punishment for offenses and bringing a person to justice are causing objections from victims. For example, in 2019 - 1097, in 2020 - 1093, in 2021 - 1102, in 2022 - 987 administrative case documents were suspended.

According to Article 36 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan, administrative punishment may be imposed no later than one year from the date of the commission of the offense, and for ongoing offenses - from the date of the detection of the offense. Also, if the initiation of a criminal case has been refused or the criminal case has been terminated, but the actions of the offender show signs of an administrative offense, the measure of administrative punishment may be applied no later than one month from the date of the decision to refuse to initiate a criminal case or terminate a criminal case, if a one-year period has not passed. At the same time, the law does not specify the period within which an administrative penalty can be imposed in cases of resumption of cases of administrative offenses suspended by pre-investigation verification bodies.

This, in turn, does not allow for the inevitability of punishment for the crime committed and creates legitimate objections from victims. In this regard, it is necessary to supplement Article 36 of the Code of Administrative Offenses with a separate part of the following content:

"In cases where the case of a suspended administrative offense is resumed by the bodies of pre-investigation verification, the administrative penalty may be applied no later than one month from the date of the decision to bring the person to administrative responsibility."

Overall, the current version of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide grounds for suspending and re-establishing administrative

proceedings, and in today's practice, the problems of applying the proposed grounds are of particular importance.

In particular, the following circumstances impede the conduct of proceedings on administrative offenses, and such circumstances require temporary suspension of proceedings:

- the person who should be involved in the case as an offender has not been identified;
- the offender is a clear person, but his whereabouts are unknown;
- the offender has left the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and it is impossible to ensure his inquiry;
- the offender has a serious and prolonged, but curable disease that excludes his participation in the proceedings.

As a result, in law enforcement practice, the possibility of suspending proceedings in cases of administrative offenses is lost, and the deadline for bringing to justice expires.

The study of the legislation of some foreign countries clearly shows how to approach this issue. For example, our opinion can also be justified by Article 28.10 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Russian Federation (suspension and resumption of proceedings in cases of administrative offenses) [5]. This norm serves as a solution to the problematic situations mentioned above.

Based on the above, in our opinion, the inclusion of separate grounds in Article 271-1 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the following content will contribute to the improvement of law enforcement practice:

"Article 271-1. Grounds for Suspension and Restoration of Proceedings on Administrative Offenses

Proceedings on administrative offenses shall be suspended and may be resumed in case of elimination of the following circumstances:

- the person who should be involved in the case as an offender has not been identified;
- the offender is a clear person, but his whereabouts are unknown;
- the offender has left the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and it is impossible to ensure his inquiry;
- the offender has a serious and prolonged, but curable disease that excludes his participation in the proceedings.

CONCLUSIONS

In our view, taking into account and implementing the aforementioned proposals:

first, further improvement of the practice of qualification of administrative offenses; secondly, it serves to eliminate the legal gaps and contradictions existing in the current legislation.

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